

Stability Indicating UPLC Method Development and Validation for The Quantification of Flubendazole and Characterization of Its Degradation Products

Mageshwari Anand*¹, P.G. Sunitha², N. Deattu², T. Hariharan², R. Hemanath², R. Jawaharsamuvel²

¹Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, College of Pharmacy, Madras Medical College (MMC) Chennai-03, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Sri Venkateswaraa Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

The RP-UPLC approach was used to produce a straightforward, accurate, and exact method for estimating flubendazole in tablet dosage form. For chromatography, stationary phase C18 column (4.6 x50 mm, 5 μm) is utilized. Acetonitrile and HPLC-grade water in 700:300 ratio was used as mobile phase compositions. The flow rate was kept at 0.45 ml/min, the detection wavelength was set at 30°C. Six standard injection was used to study the system suitability characteristics, and the finding fell well within the acceptable range. The R² value was 1.0000 after a linearity analysis was conducted at 80% to 120% level. The results showed that the precision was 0.66 for intermediate precision and 0.73 for repeatability 0.002 μg/ml and 0.006 μg/ml are the LOD and LOQ. The stress degradation study in acidic, alkaline, oxidation, thermal, photolytic and humidity conditions was used to analyse the stability indicating of the developed method LC-MS, NMR, IR and UV are used to characterize the degradation product of flubendazole OSIRIS software was used to forecast the toxicity of degraded product.

Keywords: RP-UPLC, Flubendazole, Validation, ICH Guidelines, Stability Indicating, Thermal.

INTRODUCTION

Flubendazole (FLUB); chemically is identified as, [5(4Fluorobenzoyl)1 H benzimidazol2yl] carbamic acid methyl ester¹. (Figure.1) It is a benzimidazole carbamate derivative, with an anthelmintic effect and activity against most nematodes and some other worms. Activity against some larval stages and ova has also been demonstrated. It inhibits or destroys cytoplasmic microtubules in the worm's intestinal or absorptive cells leading to inhibition of glucose uptake and depletion of glycogen stores, hence death of the worm within several days occurs².

Figure. 1: Structure of Flubendazole

Significant reductions in separation time and solvent consumption are made possible by Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC), which is specifically made to handle greater system pressures during chromatographic analysis. In addition to greater efficiency, the UPLC columns loaded with particles of 1.7 μm in size also offer the capacity to work at higher linear velocities without sacrificing efficiency, hence offering both speed and resolution advantages. Numerous applications in several

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

domains, including as pharmacy, clinical analysis, pesticide analysis, and tetracycline in human urine, have been documented using the benefits of UPLC. While UPLC columns are usually packed with particles, the UPLC is founded on the idea of using a stationary phase made up of particles smaller than 2 μ m.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT

The following criteria have been utilized to build the Flubendazole estimation method based on drug solubility and P^{ka} Value.

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Column: C₁₈ column (4.6 mm x 50 mm, 5 microns)

Mobile phase: Acetonitrile and water (700:300)

Flow rate: 0.45 ml/min

Detection wavelength: 230nm

Temperature: 30°C

Injection Volume: 5 μ L

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Preparation of Standard stock solution

20 mg of flubendazole was accurately weight and transfer in 25 ml of volumetric flask. Three-fourth of the diluent was added and sonicated for 10 minutes. The solution was made up to volume with diluent and label as standard stock solution.

Preparation of Standard working solution (100% solution)

1 mL of standard stock solution was pipetted out into a 10mL volumetric flask and makeup with 50% ACN.

Preparation of Sample solution

Twenty tablets accurately weight and the average weight of each tablet was calculated.

Weigh 20 mg Flubendazole sample into a 25 ml volumetric flask. Filter using a 0.45 μ m membrane filter after dissolving and making up the volume with 0.1M methanolic HCl.

Preparation of sample working solution (100% solution)

1 mL of standard stock solution was pipetted out into a 10mL volumetric flask and makeup with 50% ACN.

Specificity

Specificity is the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be present. Typically, these might include excipients, impurities, degradants, etc. lack of specificity of an individual analytical procedure may be compensated by other supporting analytical procedure.

Linearity and Range

The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results that are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in the sample

Precision

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements.

Accuracy

Twenty tablets was accurately weighed and average weight of each tablet was calculated. weighing and transferring roughly 20 mg of flubendazole standard into a 25 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and add 0.1M methanolic HCl to fill the volume.

Acceptance criteria:

The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0%- 102.0%.

Robustness:

Although there was no discernible difference in the outcome and the results were within the range specified by the ICH Guidelines, small intentional changes were made to the procedure, such as the flow rate and wavelength.

LOD and LOQ

LOD and LOQ were separately calculated using the calibration curve approach. By infusing increasingly

smaller amounts of the standard solution, the compound's LOD and LOQ were ascertained using the developed UPLC method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

System suitability

Following protocol, a standard solution of flubendazole was made and injected into the HPLC apparatus five times. By determining the percentage RSD of retention time, tailing factor, theoretical plates, and peak areas from five replicate injections that fall within range, standard chromatograms were used to assess the system appropriateness criteria. (Figure. 2 and Table 1)

Table 1: Peak Name – Flubendazole

Sl.no	Peak name	RT	Area	Theoretical plate count	Tailing factors
1.	Flubendazole	1.900	4616.130	2010	1.419
2.	Flubendazole	1.892	4659.480	2014	1.415
3.	Flubendazole	1.897	4593.252	2021	1.42
4.	Flubendazole	1.898	4540.714	2013	1.454
5.	Flubendazole	1.895	4503.282	2045	1.409
Mean		1.90	4582.572	2021	1.423
SD		0.003	61.632	14.22	0.018
%RSD		0.16	1.34	0.70	1.24

Figure. 2: System suitability Chromatogram

Intermediate precision

Figure. 3: Intermediate precision Chromatogram

PRECISION

Repeatability

Six working sample solutions of 80ppm are injected and the percentage amount was calculated and %RSD was found to be 0.6 and chromatogram was shown. Five working sample solutions of 80ppm are injected on the next day of the preparation of samples and the % amount found was calculated and %RSD was found to be 0.6. (Figure.3)

Linearity

To demonstrate the linearity of assay method, inject 6 standard solutions with concentrations of about 40 ppm to 120 ppm of Flubendazole. Average areas were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained for Flubendazole $y = 57.9909 x + 0.1666$ Correlation coefficient obtained was $R^2 = 1.0000$ for the Flubendazole. (Table 2)

Table 2: Linearity Concentration and Responses

Linearity Level (%)	Concentration (ppm)	Area
50	40.25	2334.26
70	56.35	3267.715
100	80.50	4667.397
125	100.62	5836.584
150	120.74	7001.531

Accuracy

Three injections of 80%, 100%, and 120% concentrations were made in triplicate, and the

recovery percentage was determined to be 99.30.(Table 3)

Table 3: Accuracy data

% Level	Sample wt. (mg)	Area	Content (mg)	Content (%)
80%	48.65	3680.158	98.870	98.87
	49.05	3679.481	98.046	98.05
	48.23	3685.468	99.875	99.88
100%	60.36	4599.361	99.593	99.59
	61.03	4600.789	98.530	98.53
	60.78	4611.145	99.158	99.16
120%	72.09	5520.360	100.086	100.09
	72.78	5528.390	99.281	99.30
	72.21	5536.158	100.206	100.21

LOD

Detection limit of the Flubendazole in this method was found to be 0.002 µg/ml.

LOQ

Detection limit of the Flubendazole in this method was found to be 0.006 µg/ml.

Robustness

Small, intentional adjustments are made to this procedure, such as temperature minus, temperature plus, mobile phase minus, mobile phase plus, flow minus, and flow plus. The above conditions %RSD is computed. (Table 4)

Table 4: Robustness Data

Parameter	%RSD
Flow Minus(0.35ml/min)	0.83%
Flow Plus(0.55ml/min)	0.55%
Wavelength Minus (228nm)	0.43%
Wavelength Plus(232nm)	0.95%

ASSAY OF MARKETED FORMULATION

Standard solution and sample solution were injected separately into the system and chromatograms were recorded and drug present in sample was calculated using before mentioned formula. (Table 5)

Table 5: Assay of Formulation

Standard	Sample	%Assay
4645.451	4621.451	99.62

STABILITY INDICATING UPLC METHOD FOR FLUBENDAZOLE

To assess the method's specificity and stability indicating qualities, stress tests were conducted. Several excipients are used when converting medications into formulations. When drugs interact with certain excipients, they change.

The acidic or basic environment of the formulation matrix may cause medications to degrade. During production, transportation, and storage, drugs may

deteriorate as a result of exposure to environmental elements such as temperature, light, humidity, etc.

Because of this, understanding the drug's breakdown route under different environmental circumstances is crucial. According to ICH recommendations, medicinal products and their active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) must undergo stress testing to determine their intrinsic stability properties.

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDY

Flubendazole was subjected to acid and alkali hydrolysis, oxidation, photo degradation and thermal stress conditions. Degradation was observed in thermal conditions.

RESULTS OF VERIFICATION PARAMETERS

Name	Retention Time	Area	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
Flubendazole	1.553	3417.386	2067	1.348
Impurity	1.555	4041.538	2129	1.375

Figure. 4: Thermal Degradation Chromatogram of Flubendazole

CHARACTERIZATION OF DEGRADED PRODUCT UV spectra (Figure-5)

Figure-5. UV spectrum of thermal Degradation product of Flubendazole

λ_{\max} of thermal Degradation product of Flubendazole was found to be **225.7nm**

Figure-6.IR spectrum of thermal Degradation product of Flubendazole

LC-MS spectrum

The degraded product obtained in the thermal stress condition was further subjected to LC-MS study for characterization and structural elucidation. (Figure-7)

Figure-7.LC-MS spectrum of thermal Degradation product of Flubendazole

NMR SPECTRUM (Figure-8)

Figure-8. NMR spectrum of thermal Degradation product of Flubendazole

Probable Degradation Pathway of Flubendazole (Figure-9)

Figure-9. Probable Degradation Pathway of Flubendazole

TOXICITY PREDICTION

The chemical structure was drawn in OSIRIS property explorer to show the biological properties of the compound. Properties like high risks of undesired effects like mutagenicity, tumorigenicity and reproductive. These effects are shown in red, green color which indicates the drug conform behaviors. (Figure10)

Figure10: Toxicity prediction of degraded product of Flubendazole by thermal degradation

CONCLUSION

To estimate the medication flubendazole in pharmaceutical dosage form, the UPLC method was created. The UPLC method was refined through the investigation of various circumstances and media. The suggested approach was validated in accordance with ICH requirements in all appropriate parameters, and the sample recoveries in each formulation were in good agreement with their corresponding labelled claims. This technique can be applied to the quality control testing of pharmaceutical dosage forms medication flubendazole. The sample exhibited varying levels of degradation under the applied stress conditions, with significant degradation observed in thermal. All major degradation products were well resolved. These results confirm the method's suitability as a stability-indicating method.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this research. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, College of Pharmacy, Madras Medical College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu for helping in carrying out this work.

FUNDING

Non-funded.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ETHICAL APPROVALS

This study does not involve experiments on animals or human subjects

REFERENCES

1. S. Budavaried, The Merck Index, An Encyclopaedia of Chemicals, Drugs and Biologicals, 13th edn., Merck & Co., Inc., (2002). Published on 15 December 2014. Downloaded by North-West University - South Africa on 21/12/2014 09:55:14.
2. Martindale, The Extra Pharmacopoeia: The Complete Drug Reference, 35th Ed., K. Proffitt (Ed.), Royal Pharmaceutical Society, London, UK (2006).
3. Takeu Higuchi and Brochmann Hanssen. Pharmaceutical Analysis. New Delhi: CBS Publishers; 2005.P.1 7.
4. Ahuja S and Jespersen Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry Elsevier, Noida. 2006.P.1 6.
5. John Taylor K. Validation of Analytical Methods- Analytical Chemistry. 198. 55(6), P. 600 6008.
6. Swartz M, Krull I. Developing and validating stability-indicating methods. LC-GC North America.2005 Jun 1:23(6):586-91.
7. P.G.Sunitha, Varalakshmi.A, K.Rama. Validated RP-HPLC PDA Method for estimation of Trientine Hydrochloride in Pharmaceutical dosage form. International Journal of ChemTech Research. 2019;12(01):87-92.
8. P.G.Sunitha, S.Hemalatha, K.Rama. Development and Validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC (PDA) Method for Estimation of Rifaximin and Ornidazole in Bulk and Combined Tablet Dosage Formulation. International Journal of ChemTech Research. 2018
9. R.Hemanath, P.G.sunitha. Novel RP-UPLC method development and validation for quantification of piroxicam tablet dosage for. International Journal of Biomedical Investigation; 2025; vol 8 (2) (165). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.31531/2581-4745/1000165>
10. P.G.Sunitha, R.Narayane. Development and Validation of Stability Indicating Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography Method for the Quantification of Teneiglipitin hydrobromide hydrate and Characterisation of its Degradation products by Spectroscopic techniques. Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences; 2017.
11. T.Hariharan, P.G. Suntha, N. Deattu. Novel RP-UPLC Method Development and Validation for Quantification of Nefopam Hydrochloride in Tablet Dosage Form. International journal of Biomedical Investigation [Internet]. 2025;vol 8(2)(163). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.31531/2581-4745.1000163>
12. A. Mageshwari, P.G. Sunitha, N.Deattu. Novel RP-UPLC Method Development and Validation

- for Quantification of flubendazole in Tablet Dosage Form. International Journal of Biomedical Investigation [Internet]. 2025;vol 8(2)(164). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.31531/2581-4745/1000164>
13. H.Mohammed idrees, P.G.Sunitha, N.Deattu. Rupanadine: a Review on Analytical Method Development and Validation for Quantification of Bulk and Pharamaceutical Dosage Form by Liquide Chromatography . <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences; 2024;vol 2(11).
 14. R.Jawaharsamuvel, P.G.Sunitha, N.Deattu. Atomoxetine: a Review on Analytical Method Development and Validation for Quantification of Bulk and Pharamaceutical Dosage Form by Liquide Chromatography . International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences. 2024;vol 2(10).
 15. P.G. Suntha, N.Deattu, P.Harikrishnan. Quantification of Ropinirole Hydrochloride in tablet by validated FTIR Spectroscopic and Colorimetric Methods. International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research. 2024 Jan 30;vol:30(1).
 16. P.G. Sunitha, N.Deattu. FTIR Specroscopic Method For the Quantitative Analysis of Topiramate in tablet. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences. 2017;Vol 6(3).
 17. P.G.Sunitha, N.Deattu,S.Banu Priya, Quantification of Azodicarbonamide in selected Food Samples by Validated RP-HPLC method and In silico Docking Study of Azodicarbonamide as a Potential Immunomodulator. International Journal of Natural Science.2023;Vol:14.
 18. P.G. Sunitha, K.Vamsee Krishna, N.Deattu. Forced Degradation Studies on Drug Products and Drug Substances and Stability Indicating Studies On Drugs-A Review. International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharamactical Research. 2023;Vol:29(1).: A Clinical Overview. JPRI. 2020; 32(30):33–39.

HOW TO CITE: Mageshwari Anand*, P.G. Sunitha, N. Deattu, T. Hariharan, R. Hemanath, R. Jawaharsamuvel, Stability Indicating UPLC Method Development and Validation for The Quantification of Flubendazole and Characterization of Its Degradation Products, J. Pharm. Sci., 2025, 1 (10), 515-523. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17390652>

